

Modeling intertwining of growing shoots

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Abstract

In recent years there has been a growing interest in developing bio-mimetic robotic devices using plants as prototypes. In particular, climbing plants capitalise on other structures to navigate through different territory and in some cases they intertwine two or more shoots forming braid-like structures through a phenomenon called intertwining. This strategy evolved by plants, is considered as a very effective way to improve their material properties and also their stability. In this work we present a mathematical model for intertwining that is based on morphoelasticity, a framework that allows us to take into account elastic effects on the plant's evolution by modeling the shoots as thin continuum Kirchhoff rods. The proposed approach can accommodate different mechanisms common among plant shoots: circumnutation, a circular periodic motion; gravitropism, the reaction to the perception of gravity; proprioception, a straightening mechanism; allotropism, sensing of other shoots; and finally point (such as a point light source) and directional tropism (such as sunlight). The model presented takes into account relevant aspects of plant physiology such as a variable bending stiffness along the shoot as well as the interplay between the different mechanisms during intertwining therefore making it amenable to bio-inspired robotic applications.

Keywords: plant bio-mechanics, morphoelasticity, bio-inspired modeling, Kirchhoff rod model

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1. Introduction

1.1. *Plants, bio-mimicry and sensing*

In recent years scientific research has been showing increasing interest into the field of bio-mimetics where seeking inspiration from nature has shown to resolve persistent problems across a variety of disciplines. One such discipline is that of bio-robotics (Mazzolai et al. (2020), Fiorello et al. (2020)) where the robots, referred to as thin continuum structures, consist of a series of appendages and joints that are controlled through the use of actuators (Walker, 2013) able to manipulate the backbone of the whole robot. In such robots, rigidity of their parts directly impacts the resulting space configuration that the structure can attain (Gallentine et al. (2020)). In particular, in situations where their principal use is to navigate and adapt through restricted environment their shape-forming capabilities and controlled regulation, through for example a variable bending stiffness profile, can be of great importance to reach their target (Must et al., 2019).

Climbing plants face similar challenges and have evolutionary developed different strategies to overcome them, such as the one investigated in this work which is intertwining. With this strategy climbing plants intertwine individual stems so as to reach at a greater length and increase the bending stiffness of the whole structure Gallentine et al. (2020). As documented in some relevant works such as Silk and Holbrook (2005), Isnard et al. (2009)) where a shoot - pole interaction was studied, such phenomenon involves a tension generation mechanism that is created through frictional contact. In order to take advantage of this technique in the field of bio-inspired applications, a mathematical model is needed able to reproduce the desired intertwining behaviour taking into account the above characteristics. Since mechanical forces impact directly on the deformation of the shoot, namely through a constitutive relation, it is of fundamental importance that the modeling procedure includes elastic effects, and investigate what is their impact on the resulting behaviour of the shoot. In the current literature, there are different models for describing the evolution of one shoot while a mathematical model for the intertwining is to the authors' knowledge absent.

In modelling growing shoots the first step is the consideration of the sensing mechanisms. Plants are known to exhibit different behaviours when growing, referred to as nastic or tropic movements (Darwin and Darwin, 1896), (Gilroy, 2008). The first are due to internal drivers such as circumnutation, that is the periodic motion of a plant related to search processes. On the other hand, tropisms are growth driven responses in the direction of a stimulus (towards or away from it) such as gravity, light, or other plants relevant for example to root systems (see *e.g.* Bastien et al. (2019)). The modeling of sensing mechanisms has led to deeper understanding of the growth processes in plants regarding the signals that should be taken into account and how these are related to the differential growth that drives the motion of the plants (Meroz (2021), Porat et al. (2020), Bressan et al. (2017), Bastien et al. (2015), Bastien and Meroz (2016)).

1.2. Adding mechanics: morphoelasticity

Although the above studies have been concentrated on the important aspect of sensing, a fundamental concept to take into account for a more realistic modeling is that of elasticity. Plants are made of biological material that through differential growth is subjected to stress- or strain-induced deformation. The influence of mechanics on plant growth has been made relevant in many works. For example in Chelakkot and Mahadevan (2017) it was shown through nondimensional analysis, that the competition between sensing and elasticity can lead to many possible configurations for a growing shoot. In fact, it was shown that for some material properties, elasticity effects become more prevalent than sensing effects such as in the case of soft and heavy growing shoots, characteristic of real plants. In O'Reilly and Trexler (2011) the effect of taper and secondary growth was studied, in Senan et al. (2008) branching, Agostinelli et al. (2020), studied the effect of delayed proprioception and gravitropism. Finally in Vecchiato et al. (2022) the effects of variable mass distribution and secondary growth were studied and their impact on the final reach and orientation of the shoot was investigated. All these studies included the effect of self-weight that had a very high impact on the resulting structure of the shoot underlying the importance of forces.

From the modeling point of view, incorporating mechanical effects in plants is a rather non-trivial procedure since the effect of growth is to continuously alter the internal stresses developed along the structure (Niklas, 1992). Central role in the construction of the mechanical models of growing shoots is that of morphoelasticity (Goriely (2017), Moulton et al. (2013),

Moulton et al. (2020b)). This is a concept related to morphogenesis (Ambrosi et al., 2011) i.e. how biological organisms acquire their form (from - $\mu\omicron\rho\phi\eta'$ meaning form in greek), is used among diverse fields from polymers (Kadapa (2021), Kadapa and Hossain (2022)) to soft structure modeling (Dervaux and Amar, 2008), molluscs (Rudraraju et al., 2019) or sea shells (Moulton et al., 2020a). The principle of morphoelasticity in modeling biological growth is to decompose the total deformation into growth-induced and elasticity-induced deformation using the so called multiplicative decomposition (Rodriguez et al. (1994), Sadik and Yavari (2017)). In this work our goal is to study the intertwining between two individual stems and also their interaction therefore our model is based on the above framework which allows to tackle the problem of growth and elasticity-induced deformation using notions from continuum mechanics and therefore evaluating explicitly the evolution of the plants' motion and its response to mechanical loads.

1.3. Modeling interactions and contact

Another key point is that of modeling interactions such as twining around a support, contact with walls or other structures including plants e.g. the collective behaviour approach in Bastien et al. (2019). There are different studies that highlight the importance of contact forces in the subsequent motion of climbing plants (Isnard et al. (2009), Goriely and Neukirch (2006), Silk and Holbrook (2005), Moulton et al. (2020c), Rowe and Speck (2015)). In these works where the contact between a shoot and a support is investigated it is demonstrated that the plant's ascend onto a rigid support results from a tension generating mechanism able to create a squeezing force towards the support. This generated tension is a result of friction and plants use it to have better stability. Indeed in this work by including frictional contact between two intertwining shoots we demonstrate that this increases their bending stiffness. Other studies that dealt with frictional contact but with application to root systems and not shoots, are those of Sipos and Várkonyi (2022) and Zhang et al. (2022) where the root-soil interaction in the case of *Arabidopsis Thaliana* was studied. The authors found that mechanical stress due to frictional contact produced various experimentally observed morphological patterns such as skewing, coiling, and waving. The above results underpin the importance of contact forces in the dynamics of the plant growth. Specifically, since climbing plants use their surroundings to climb, the present work considers the coupling of the dynamics between different shoots as well as evaluating the forces arising from their interaction.

1.4. *This work*

In this paper we present a three-dimensional mathematical model for the intertwining of growing shoots that is based on morphoelasticity theory for Kirchhoff rods drawing inspiration from the works of Porat et al. (2020) and Agostinelli et al. (2020). Specifically, we present a model that in the single shoot case successfully accommodates a variety of tropisms while differently from other approaches, it exhibits point tropism (a stimulus whose source is a point located at a point \mathbf{r}_p in space) and directional tropism (a stimulus whose source is along the direction \mathbf{n}) *combined* with elasticity. Additionally, we present the main contribution of this work that is the intertwining describing the sensing and interaction between two growing shoots.

The morphoelasticity framework permits us to include all the relevant mechanical interactions and the deformation they induce upon the stem, therefore such an addition provides a more realistic model. To this end we include gravity and friction.

From a biomechanics point of view this gives the possibility of measuring forces that are otherwise difficult to obtain in a laboratory environment. Therefore, in practice the model gives access to the mechanical quantities involved in the intertwining process such as forces, moments, strains and bending and torsional stiffness. This information is invaluable in the design of bio-inspired robots taking inspiration from plant biomechanics. For these reasons we hope it will be a valuable tool for other researchers.

The three-dimensional mathematical model is presented in a way that will highlight the exact factors and quantities that play central role as building blocks of the system.

Given the above, the paper is organised as follows: section 2 describes the mathematical model for the case of one shoot, based on the Kirchhoff rod theory formalism, defining the governing equations that relate the strain developed along the shoot to the external and internal signals. Then in section 3, based on the single shoot model we proceed introducing the governing equations for the intertwining problem followed by the modeling of their contact. In section 4, we discuss the values of the physical parameters used in the model. In section 5, we perform numerical simulations for a number of key examples, including responses to different stimuli, such as circumnutation, gravitropism and proprioception in combination with directional and point tropism that demonstrate the qualitative agreement of the proposed model. We continue with numerical simulations of the intertwining

Figure 1: Plot of the centerline with the directors vectors $\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$ and the global reference system xyz .

phenomenon considering the scenario of simultaneous point tropism and allotropism while taking into account the effect of contact. Finally, in section 6, a discussion on the results is presented and the conclusions of this work are listed.

2. 3D description of a shoot as a Kirchhoff rod

We start describing the model for one shoot where the geometry of the shoot is that of a long thin cylinder. Then the shoot can be considered as a Kirchhoff rod (O'Reilly, 2017) described through its centerline $\mathbf{r}(s, t)$ where t is time and s is the arc-length. At each cross-section along the rod we assign an orthogonal basis of vectors called directors $\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$, such that the vectors $\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2$ span the cross-section and $\mathbf{d}_3 = \mathbf{d}_1 \times \mathbf{d}_2$. The evolution of this director basis allows us to describe the evolution of the rod through space according to the so-called Darboux vector

$$\partial_s \mathbf{d}_j = \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{d}_j, \quad j = 1, 2, 3, \quad (1)$$

as shown in figure 1

The components $u_j = \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{d}_j$, $j = 1, 2, 3$ describe the deformation of the local basis with respect to a global reference frame, here set as the origin

$Oxyz$, and they are a measure of flexural strain for $j = 1, 2$ and torsional strain for $j = 3$.

We assume that the tangent to the centerline is always parallel to \mathbf{d}_3 , which translates into the condition

$$\partial_s \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{d}_3. \quad (2)$$

Plants move through differential growth, that is the unequal elongation on each side of the organ (antidiametrically placed in the case of a stem with a circular cross-section) which is the result of reaction to internal and external signals (see e.g. Bastien et al. (2014)). Following similar arguments as in Porat et al. (2020) and Bastien and Meroz (2016), the motion due to differential growth is described using the following equations

$$\frac{Du_1^*}{Dt} = \frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{r} \mathbf{\Delta} \cdot \mathbf{d}_1, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{Du_2^*}{Dt} = \frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{r} \mathbf{\Delta} \cdot \mathbf{d}_2, \quad (4)$$

where $(\cdot)^*$ corresponds to the intrinsic strain, ϵ is the growth function, r is the radius of the shoot, $\mathbf{\Delta}(s, t)$ is the differential growth vector that is defined in the following for the different cases of tropisms we consider in this work. We refer to u_1^* and u_2^* as the intrinsic (actual) bending strains about \mathbf{d}_1 and \mathbf{d}_2 respectively where u_1 and u_2 are the visible strains of the shoot. The material derivative $D/Dt := \partial/\partial t + v\partial/\partial s$ expresses the material elongation that accompanies differential growth with velocity

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = v(s, t) = \int_0^s \dot{\epsilon}(\sigma, t) d\sigma, \quad (5)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the local growth rate. Additionally, we assume that this elongation takes places only in the sub-apical part of the plant: $l - l_g \leq s \leq l$ and it is zero otherwise (see e.g. (Bastien et al., 2019)).

With regards to the differential growth vector, it is known that the relevant directional information of any stimulus lies within its perpendicular projection to the organ surface (Porat et al., 2020) that in our case is the plane defined by the director vectors $\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2$ that span the cross-section of the plant. In the case of one shoot we study the evolution under the action of different phenomena such as circumnutation, gravitropism, proprioception, point tropism, and directional tropism and in the intertwining case, allotropism.

As demonstrated in Bastien et al. (2015), these different mechanisms can be considered additive therefore the differential vector is constructed adding up the individual terms and thus it is written as

$$\Delta = \sum_k \Delta_k, \quad (6)$$

where k is the subscript corresponding to any stimuli among c : circumnutation, g : gravitropism, p : proprioception, pt : point tropism, dt : directional tropism that are defined as follows

$$\Delta_c = \lambda_c \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau_c}\right) + \lambda_c \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau_c}\right), \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta_g = -\lambda_g \mathbf{d}_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 + \lambda_g \mathbf{d}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_3, \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta_p = -\lambda_p u_1(s, t) - \lambda_p u_2(s, t), \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta_{pt} = -\lambda_{pt} \mathbf{d}_2 \cdot \mathbf{d}_{mp} + \lambda_{pt} \mathbf{d}_1 \cdot \mathbf{d}_{mp}, \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta_{dt} = -\lambda_{dt} \mathbf{d}_2 \cdot \mathbf{d}_{dt} - \lambda_{dt} \mathbf{d}_1 \cdot \mathbf{d}_{dt}, \quad (11)$$

where the constants $\lambda_{(\cdot)}$ denote the corresponding sensing parameter, and $\mathbf{d}_{(\cdot)}$ are the corresponding vectors pointing from the shoot to the external stimulus position (see Porat et al. (2020)).

As an example we refer to the case of a single shoot undergoing circumnutation, proprioception and gravitropism. Then the governing equations take the following form

$$\dot{u}_1^* = \overbrace{\lambda_c \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s, t)}{r} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau_c}\right)}^{\text{circumnutation}} - \overbrace{\lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s, t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_3}^{\text{gravitropism}} - \overbrace{\lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s, t) u_1(s, t)}^{\text{proprioception}}, \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{u}_2^* = \lambda_c \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s, t)}{r} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau_c}\right) + \lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s, t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 - \lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s, t) u_2(s, t), \quad (13)$$

Additionally, we are interested in forces such as gravity taken into account through self-weight while another possible choice is wind resistance resulting in drag forces (Niklas, 1998). These forces cause elastic deformation and

are included solving an additional set of equations, the Kirchhoff equations, which describe the balance of linear and angular momentum along the shoot. Since the time-scale of mechanical equilibrium is much slower than the time scale for plant growth (Chelakkot and Mahadevan, 2017), these equations are solved in their static form

$$\mathbf{n}'(s) + \mathbf{f}(s) = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{m}'(s) + \mathbf{d}_3(s, t) \times \mathbf{n}(s) = 0. \quad (15)$$

Since in this section we consider only one shoot, $\mathbf{f}(s)$ is equal to the force of gravity \mathbf{f}_{gr} due to the weight of the shoot defined as:

$$\mathbf{f}_{gr}(s) = -\rho \mathbf{g} A, \quad (16)$$

where ρ is the mass density per unit length, \mathbf{g} is the acceleration of gravity, A is the area of the cross-section, and l is the total length.

The shoot is considered isotropic and linearly elastic, therefore the relevant constitutive law in order to couple the visible strains u_j to intrinsic ones u_j^* is the following

$$\mathbf{m} = \sum_j B_j (u_j - u_j^*) \cdot \mathbf{d}_j, \quad j = 1, 2, 3. \quad (17)$$

The quantities B_j , $j = 1, 2, 3$ are defined as: $B_1 = E I_1$, $B_2 = E I_2$, $B_3 = G J$, corresponding to bending stiffness B_1 , B_2 and torsional stiffness B_3 , while E is the Young modulus, G is the shear modulus defined as $G = 2E(1 + \nu)$, and ν is the Poisson ratio.

In this work we consider that the stems has circular cross sections therefore the Finally as to the second moment of inertia I we assume that the stem has circular cross section therefore the principal moments of inertia, I_1, I_2 and the polar moment of inertia J are

$$I_1 = I_2 = I = \frac{J}{2} = \frac{\pi R^4}{4}. \quad (18)$$

This leads us to a single expression for the bending stiffnesses defined in the section 4 regarding the selection of physical parameters.

Finally, in order to track the motion of the local reference frame attached to the stem, defined by the directors \mathbf{d}_j , to the global Cartesian reference system \mathbf{e}_j , a rotation matrix $\mathbf{R} = [\mathbf{d}_1 || \mathbf{d}_2 || \mathbf{d}_3]$ is introduced and is discretized

using Euler angles χ, ϕ, ψ given by the following matrix (see for example Fonseca and De Aguiar (2000))

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} c(\chi)c(\psi)c(\phi) - s(\chi)s(\phi) & c(\chi)c(\psi)s(\phi) + s(\chi)c(\phi) & -c(\chi)s(\phi) \\ -s(\chi)c(\psi)c(\phi) - c(\chi)s(\phi) & -s(\chi)c(\psi)s(\phi) + c(\chi)c(\phi) & s(\chi)s(\psi) \\ s(\psi)c(\phi) & s(\psi)s(\phi) & c(\psi) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (19)$$

where c, s are the cosine and sine functions respectively.

3. Modeling intertwining

The phenomenon of intertwining that is the braiding of individual stems met among some species of plants, is an effective solution for them when they need to bridge gaps between supports. It is this strategy that can be investigated and translated accordingly into a bio-inspired innovative robotic solution. Building on our understanding due to the single shoot case we now present the case of intertwining where we consider the following scenario. For the first shoot (master shoot) we consider the case of point tropism in addition to gravitropism and proprioception. For the second shoot (slave shoot) we consider its corresponding gravitropic and proprioceptive terms while we add a term denoting the tropism towards the other shoot. This so-called allotropic term (Bastien et al., 2019), is responsible for the sensing of the nearby shoot, thus is composed of a vector that drives the second shoot towards the first. In the following subscript m refers to the master shoot and s to the slave shoot and the system of equations for the two shoots is thus

$$\dot{u}_{1_m}^* = -\lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s_m, t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_{2m} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2 - \lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s_m, t) u_{1_m}(s_m, t) - \overbrace{\lambda_{pt} \dot{\epsilon}(s_m, t) \mathbf{d}_{2m} \cdot \mathbf{d}_{mp}}^{\text{point tropism}}, \quad (20)$$

$$\dot{u}_{2_s}^* = +\lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s_m, t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_{1m} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2 - \lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s_m, t) u_{2_m}(s_m, t) + \lambda_{pt} \dot{\epsilon}(s_m, t) \mathbf{d}_{1m} \cdot \mathbf{d}_{mp}, \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{u}_{1_s}^* = -\lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s_s, t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_{2s} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2 - \lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s_s, t) u_{1_s}(s_s, t) - \overbrace{\lambda_a \dot{\epsilon}(s_s, t) \mathbf{d}_{2s} \cdot \mathbf{d}_{sm}}^{\text{allotropism}}, \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{u}_{2_s}^* = +\lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s_s, t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_{1s} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2 - \lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s_s, t) u_{2_s}(s_s, t) + \lambda_a \dot{\epsilon}(s_s, t) \mathbf{d}_{1s} \cdot \mathbf{d}_{sm}, \quad (23)$$

where the distance vector between the master shoot and the point of tropism is

$$\mathbf{d}_{mp} = \frac{\mathbf{r}_p - \mathbf{r}_m}{|\mathbf{r}_p - \mathbf{r}_m|} \quad (24)$$

while the distance vector between master shoot and slave shoot is

$$\mathbf{d}_{sm} = \frac{\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_s}{|\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_s|}. \quad (25)$$

The position of each shoot is given by the integration of the corresponding tangent vector $\mathbf{d}_{3(\cdot)}$, as

$$\mathbf{r}'_m(s_m, t) = \mathbf{d}_{3m} \rightarrow \begin{cases} x'_m(s_m) &= d_{m33} = \cos(\psi_m) \\ y'_m(s_m) &= d_{m32} = \sin(\psi_m)\cos(\phi_m) \\ z'_m(s_m) &= d_{m31} = \sin(\psi_m)\sin(\phi_m) \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

and similarly for the second shoot

$$\mathbf{r}'_s(s_s, t) = \mathbf{d}_{3s} \rightarrow \begin{cases} x'_s(s_s) &= d_{s33} = \cos(\psi_s) \\ y'_s(s_s) &= d_{s32} = \sin(\psi_s)\cos(\phi_s) \\ z'_s(s_s) &= d_{s31} = \sin(\psi_s)\sin(\phi_s) \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

3.1. External forces

We take into account contact and frictional interactions between the intertwining shoots. This is accomplished by adding the relevant force terms due to contact and friction into the static equilibrium equations of each individual shoot, leading to

$$\mathbf{n}'(s) + \mathbf{f}(s) = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{m}'(s) + \mathbf{d}_3(s, t) \times \mathbf{n}(s) = 0, \quad (29)$$

for $s = s_m, s_s$ for the master and slave shoot respectively. For forces we consider gravity and contact with friction

$$\mathbf{f}(s) = \mathbf{f}_{gr}(s) + \mathbf{f}_c(s), \quad (30)$$

As for the contact force we select the following form

$$\mathbf{f}_c(s) = -g(d) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_s}{|\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_s|}, \quad (31)$$

where the function g is

$$g(d) = \begin{cases} g_{max}(1 - \tanh(k g_{max}^{-1} d)), & d > 0, \\ g_{max} + k d, & d \leq 0, \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

and $d = |\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_s| - 2R$ represents the penetration distance between the shoots in order to account for the intensity of the force. The constant k expresses the rigidity between the two shoots when these are in contact and is estimated using the formula following which holds in the case of two thin cylinders in contact (Popov et al., 2010)

$$k = \frac{\pi}{8} \frac{E}{1 - \nu}, \quad (33)$$

where E is the Young modulus and ν is the Poisson ratio. For the selected values of parameters (see section 4) is of the order of $10MPa$, here we use $k = 100$ in order to avoid instability of the solver. The maximum value is approximated analytically for two parallel cylinders with $g_{max} = 0.15N/m$ (see Sipos and Várkonyi (2022) and references therein). Varying this parameter in the interval $0.1 - 1$ did not show impact on the result. With regards to friction, following Silk and Holbrook (2005), the friction force between the two shoots is considered to be purely tangential to the normal force multiplied by the friction coefficient μ_{fr} which is chosen in the range $[0, 3]$.

4. Selection of physical parameters

In this paragraph we discuss the choice of the physical parameters used in the model in order to study the phenomenon of intertwining in the case of *Aristolochia macrophylla* shoots. For this reason we set realistic values for the parameters based on experimental data provided by the Plant Biomechanics Group of the Albert-Ludwigs University in Freiburg.

Typical values for the radius of the stems are between $0.001 - 0.005m$ and in our simulations we fix this value at $0.005m$. The mass value lies in the range of $1gr \leq m \leq 4gr$. The typical value of the total stem length is in the range of $5cm \leq l \leq 20cm$. The acceleration of gravity is $\mathbf{g} = 9.81m/s^2$. Thus we set the value for mass density equal to $\rho = 1000kg/m^3$, and the length to $10cm$. The initial length of the stems is chosen as $l_0 = 10cm$ and the length of the growth zone is taken equal $l_g = 10cm$.

To mimic physical reality, bending stiffness is considered variable along the shoot. This is due to the fact that as real plant stems grow the parts near its apex are fresher and less rigid a property that might facilitate faster movement and grabbing while the parts near the base are becoming gradually stiffer through a lignification process. This results in a non-homogeneous distribution of the bending stiffness along the shoot that has a steady profile (Rivière et al., 2020). To incorporate this into our model using the function (Chelakkot and Mahadevan, 2017)

$$B(s, t) = B_{max} - (B_{max} - B_0)e^{max\{0, t-t_l\}}, \quad (34)$$

where t_l is the lignification time set in days, B_{max} and B_0 is the maximum and minimum value of the bending stiffness correspondingly with values $B_{max} = 20000 \text{ N mm}^2$ and $B_0 = 200 \text{ N mm}^2$.

We would like to note that all of these values are consistent with others found in bibliography (Köhler et al. (2000), Chelakkot and Mahadevan (2017), Agostinelli et al. (2020), Vecchiato et al. (2022)).

The sensing parameters were estimated after visual comparison of the simulated result with photos of *Aristolochia macrophylla*. Their resulting corresponding ranges used in the simulations are: circumnutation $0 \leq \lambda_c \leq 1.5$, gravitropic sensitivity $-1 \leq \lambda_g \leq 0$, where its negative value is due to the fact that as reported in Bastien et al. (2019), stems as opposed to roots, exhibit negative gravitropism. Following is the proprioceptive sensitivity with $0 \leq \lambda_p \leq 2$, point tropism sensitivity $0 \leq \lambda_{pt} \leq 3$, directional tropism sensitivity $0 \leq \lambda_{dt} \leq 3$ and finally allotropic sensitivity $0 \leq \lambda_a \leq 3$.

5. Case examples and simulations

Here we illustrate the capabilities of the model in different cases. We demonstrate how the model can be applied to a variety of different scenarios by considering the stimuli through the differential growth vector. The goal is to show that the model presented can reproduce the experimental observations, demonstrating thus its relevance for investigating a variety of tropisms as well as interactions between shoots.

5.1. Directional tropism

The first stimulus that is presented is the directional, then the relevant differential growth vector is

$$\Delta = \Delta_g + \Delta_p + \Delta_{dt} \quad (35)$$

Parameter	Name	SI Units
λ_c	circumnutation intensity	-
λ_g	gravitropic sensitivity	-
λ_p	proprioceptive sensitivity	-
λ_{pt}	point tropism sensitivity	-
λ_{dt}	directional tropism sensitivity	-
λ_a	allotropic sensitivity	-
t_s	scaling time	[s]
t_g	growth time	[s]
t_c	circumnutation time	[s]
t_l	lignification time	[s]
\mathbf{g}	acceleration of gravity	$[m/s^2]$
L_0	initial length	[m]
l_g	growth zone length	[m]
r	radius	[m]
ρ	mass density	$[\text{kg} / m^3]$
E	Young's modulus	[Pa], $[N/m^2]$
ν	Poisson's ratio	-
G	shear modulus	-
B_1, B_2	bending stiffness	$[Nm^2]$
B_3	torsional stiffness	$[Nm^2]$
A	cross sectional area	$[m^2]$
I	second moment of inertia	$[m^4]$
J	polar moment of inertia	$[m^4]$
μ_{fr}	friction coefficient	-
k	shoot rigidity	[Pa]

Table 1: Overview of the parameters of the model, their symbol, name and units in SI

leading to the following governing equations

$$\dot{u}_1^* = - \overbrace{\lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s,t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_3}^{\text{gravitropism}} - \overbrace{\lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s,t) u_1(s,t)}^{\text{proprioception}} - \overbrace{\lambda_{dt} \dot{\epsilon}(s,t) \mathbf{d}_2 \cdot \mathbf{d}_{dt}}^{\text{directional tropism}}, \quad (36)$$

$$\dot{u}_2^* = + \lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s,t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 - \lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s,t) u_2(s,t) + \lambda_{dt} \dot{\epsilon}(s,t) \mathbf{d}_1 \cdot \mathbf{d}_{dt}, \quad (37)$$

where \mathbf{d}_{dt} is the direction of the stimulus. The result can be seen in figure 2 where the shoot is plotted along with some relevant quantities on the body. As expected, the internal force n_2 (corresponding to the component of \mathbf{n} along \mathbf{d}_3) is dominated by the weight of the shoot, this in return creates a moment m_3 along the tangent direction of the shoot. Accordingly the intrinsic strains are consistent with the configuration of the shoot in space with the larger ones generated around points of inflexion of the shoot.

Additionally, numerical simulations showed that not including gravitropism causes the forces n_1, n_2 , the moments m_1, m_2 and the intrinsic strains u_1^*, u_2^* (blue and orange line respectively) to superimpose as shown in figure 3. These tests demonstrate the impact of including mechanical deformation in an otherwise dynamical model as the picture might be incomplete without them. This impact becomes more evident in the case of point tropism, as will be shown in the next section 5.2.

Finally inclusion of circumnutation has not shown any nontrivial behaviour other than oscillating quantities, and thus it was omitted. However the relevant simulation is provided in the supplementary material.

5.2. Point tropism

This type of stimulus shows the capability of the model to exhibit point tropism whose source is a point located at \mathbf{r}_p (Bastien et al., 2019) and with the mechanisms of gravitropism and proprioception also included. In this case the differential growth vector is constructed adding the contribution of gravitropism, proprioception and point tropism

$$\Delta = \Delta_g + \Delta_p + \Delta_{pt}, \quad (38)$$

Figure 2: The case of a directional stimulus. The shoot evolves towards the direction $(-1, 1, 0)$ under proprioception and gravitropism.

Figure 3: The case of a directional stimulus. The shoot evolves towards the direction $(-1, 1, 0)$ under only proprioception and without gravitropism.

leading to the following governing equations

$$\dot{u}_1^* = - \overbrace{\lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s, t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_3}^{\text{gravitropism}} - \overbrace{\lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s, t) u_1(s, t)}^{\text{proprioception}} - \overbrace{\lambda_{pt} \dot{\epsilon}(s, t) \mathbf{d}_2 \cdot \mathbf{d}_{pt}}^{\text{point tropism}}, \quad (39)$$

$$\dot{u}_2^* = + \lambda_g \frac{\dot{\epsilon}(s, t)}{r} \mathbf{d}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 - \lambda_p \dot{\epsilon}(s, t) u_2(s, t) + \lambda_{pt} \dot{\epsilon}(s, t) \mathbf{d}_1 \cdot \mathbf{d}_{pt}, \quad (40)$$

where \mathbf{d}_{pt} is the distance vector between the shoot and the point of tropism given as

$$\mathbf{d}_{pt} = \frac{\mathbf{r}_p - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_p - \mathbf{r}|}. \quad (41)$$

The result of the simulation is shown in figure 4, where successive time instants of the point tropism case are visualised. From this figure it can be appreciated the fact that the variable bending stiffness along the shoot according to equation (34) results into the characteristic curved profile near the tip, reminiscent of young plant stems, that would be not possible if the bending stiffness was taken constant along the shoot's length (Rivière et al., 2020). Additionally in this case we find that the effect of the gravitropism on the evolution is a non-trivial one. The relevant simulated result is shown in figure 5 where the case of point tropism with and without gravitropism are shown (top and bottom of the figure respectively). From the figure it is shown that the case with gravitropism leads to the generation of greater strains. Additionally it is noticed that the addition of the gravitropic signal results in more regular twining. This is evident at later times in the simulation seen in figure 6 where the case without gravitropism shows a characteristic knot-like structure which is absent in the case with gravitropism. We also found that, the inclusion of the weight of the shoot accelerates even more the twining around the point of tropism. On the basis of what was presented in the case of the directional tropism in section 5.1 this can be explained by the greater strains generated therefore causing larger tension along the shoot and thus more bending. We would like to stress that the above numerical experiments demonstrate how important is the inclusion of mechanics in the plant growth process since it impacts significantly on the resulting morphological pattern as well as mechanical loads that develop during the growth process.

5.3. Intertwining

We now turn our attention to the case of intertwining. Following the numerical solution of the system of equations (20) - (29) we show in figure

Figure 4: From a to i: the evolution of one shoot under gravitropism, proprioception and point tropism.

Figure 5: Top view: overview of the instantaneous moments and intrinsic strains when gravitropism is not taken into consideration. Bottom view: overview of the instantaneous moments and intrinsic strains when gravitropism is taken into consideration.

Figure 6: Taking into consideration gravitropism, makes the twining around a point more regular.

7 a comparison between two real intertwined shoots of *Aristolochia Macrophylla* and the corresponding simulated result. It can be seen that the model reproduces the intertwining between the two shoots, capturing the structure of the two shoots. In figure 8 successive time instants of the simulation of the two intertwining stems are shown.

5.3.1. Impact of intertwining on the bending stiffness

In this paragraph we investigate the role of forces on the bending stiffness. In order to assess its impact in a comparative manner we analyse the behaviour of the master shoot in the case of two intertwined shoots and then compare it with the results for the single shoot case.

Figure 9 shows the quantities obtained from the numerical simulations of the intertwining. Three different cases are shown, each one corresponding to a different value of the friction coefficient. To assess the impact of friction we selected $\mu_{fr} \in \{0 - 3\}$ thus varying from frictionless to frictional contact. Starting from the morphology of the shoots (top of the figure 9) we found that there is no apparent difference regarding the configuration of the two shoots.

Regarding the internal forces are dominated by the gravity force. As for the friction, an increase in the friction coefficient has a marginal effect on the internal forces that is observed mainly on the tension/axial force n_3 (the internal force along \mathbf{d}_3 , which is tangent to the shoot).

The internal moments are large close to the extremities of the master shoot, that is at the base of the shoot with a small peak at the tip in agreement with the fact that larger strain develop there. However there is no noticeable impact on the moments.

Figure 7: A comparison between experimental data (top) and the results obtained from the simulation of intertwining (bottom).

Importantly, the intrinsic strains shown in figure 9 are consistent with the configuration of the master shoot in space as for the case of the single shoot shown in figure 2.

Finally regarding the effect of friction on the bending stiffness is seen in the last three lines of the figure 9. Increasing the coefficient from 0 to 1 has no effect on either of B_j but increasing from 1 to 3 leads to a decrease on B_2 .

For comparison, we evaluate the bending and torsional stiffness for the master shoot when this evolves individually in the case of point tropism. The result, shown in figure 10, shows that for the individual shoot, the maximum values of the torsional and bending stiffness are significantly higher in comparison to the case when the frictional interaction with the slave shoot is considered. Therefore this suggests that friction has a negative impact on the bending stiffness of the shoot.

6. Discussion and Conclusions

In this paper we have presented a general three-dimensional model for the intertwining of plant shoots with a mathematical formulation that takes into account elasticity. Additionally we have presented the case of multiple

Figure 8: From a to l: successive time instants of two shoots intertwining.

Figure 9: Left to right: impact of increasing the friction coefficient on the computed quantities such as shoot morphology, internal forces, internal moments, intrinsic strains and bending and torsional stiffness for three different values of the friction coefficient 0, 1, 3.

Figure 10: Instantaneous quantities for the case of one shoot with point tropism. From left to right: configuration in space of the shoot, bending and torsional stiffness and internal forces, internal moments and intrinsic strains.

tropisms and specifically the point tropism and directional tropism coupled with proprioception and gravitropism with elastic effects being included. We have constructed the model in the framework of morphoelasticity where the shoots were modelled as Kirchhoff rods.

Through the model we presented some relevant aspects of plants that can be directly translated into useful information therefore making the proposed model amenable to bio-inspired robotics applications. Specifically we described how plants can adapt their shape and respond to multiple tropisms as need in the design of soft robotic arms (Trivedi et al., 2008). We have also underpinned the role of mechanics and the importance of using a variable bending stiffness along the stem. All these aspects become relevant in the design of robotic devices and can have important effect for their realisation (Naselli and Mazzolai, 2021), (Must et al., 2019).

We have verified the model through a qualitative comparison with shoots of *Aristolochia macrophylla* showing its ability to capture morphological patterns of the intertwining phenomenon between two growing shoots.

We have showed the generality of the present approach in combining different kinds of tropisms such as circumnutation, directional tropism and point tropism, gravitropism, proprioception and allotropism with the case of intertwining.

We found that the effect of gravitropism has a non-trivial behaviour in the case of point tropism. Specifically, we found that it accelerates twining and has a regularising effect when taken into account.

We found that with regards to the forces that are generated during intertwining, these are dominated by the gravity force while axial tensions showed a marginal increase. Finally we found that friction has a negative impact on the bending stiffness of the shoot.

Though the model developed here has successfully reproduced the evolution of growing shoots both in the case of single shoot and intertwining shoots, there are other aspects that can be taken into account. Among them is the effect of elliptic cross sections characterising the geometry of the shoots, the impact of variable mass distribution along the shoot, or branching processes Senan et al. (2008). These additions can be incorporated to the model and their impact on the final morphology of the shoot can be tested. Other possible direction of research is investigating how intertwining can impact on the final reach of the shoot as studied (Vecchiato et al., 2022). Finally, another possible improvement is a detailed experimental validation, that is left for future work.

The model presented allows for a possible approach towards better understanding of the intertwining phenomenon in the framework of morphoelasticity. It is known that apart from the sensing processes also forces impact the evolution of plant shoots. An example in this work was the impact of the gravitropism on the internal forces. This is also another aspect that needs to be taken into account in the design of bio mimetic devices. Therefore the use of morphoelastic models to study such physical systems gives important insight since there is direct access to stress induced elastic deformations and related quantities of interest such as bending stiffness. In this work, by taking these factors into account, we have shown how this framework can be used to reproduce realistic plant behaviour and extract useful information for the mechanics of the growing shoots.

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